

EMPLOYEE AND EMPLOYER SATISFACTION IN KAYAL AGRO FOODS, MADURAI, TAMILNADU

M. Bhavithra* & Dr. B. Velmurugan**

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Employee satisfaction is important to management because they determine the behaviour of workers in the organization. The commonly held opinion is that "A satisfied worker is a productive worker", a satisfied work force will create a pleasant atmosphere within the organization to perform well, and hence job satisfaction has become a major topic for research studies. The specific problem addressed in this study is to examine the impact of job satisfaction on performance. It considered which rewards (intrinsic and extrinsic) determine job satisfaction of an employee. It also considered influence of age, gender and experience of employees on level of job satisfaction. In addition it investigated in most satisfying event of an employee in the job, why employees stay and leave the organization. Data were collected through a field survey using a questionnaire from the employee groups, namely Professionals, Managers and Non-managers from organizations covering Kayal Agro Foods. The analysis data revealed that there exists positive correlation between job satisfaction and performance of employees.

Company Profile:

Kayal Agro Foods in Natham, Dindigul is known to satisfactorily capture to the demands of its customer base. It stands located at 110/1 Pannuvarpatti, Kovilpatti Post, Natham Tk, Natham 624401. The business strives to make for a positive experience through its offerings. Customer centricity is at the core of Kayal Agro Foods in Natham, Dindigul and it is this belief that has led the business to build long-term relationships. Ensuring a positive customer experience, making available goods and and/or services that are of top-notch quality is given prime importance. Kindly scroll up for the address and contact details of Kayal Agro Foods in Dindigul. Kayal Agro Foods was established in 2015 with health and nutrition in mind. Kayal Agro Foods is the child company of KRK Exports which was started in 2004 as an exporting house with great quality and standards. Within a short span of time KRK Exports grew multiple folds becoming a one-star export house. KRK Exports, the decades old organisation, in a mission to deliver best goods to the consumer by themselves, ventured into Kayal Agro Foods. Our offices are located in Madurai and Dindigul district of South Tamil Nadu. The manufacturing facility, spanning across 50+ acres is located at Natham (Dindigul District) in a beautiful scenic rural environment. White labelling services are also part of our establishment. Our quality products enable the market leader to rebrand, restyle and in turn them under their label or trademark. We believe in one thing: "Good Food". Food makes everybody happy and it brings us together.

The Importance of the Employer-Employee Relationship The relationship between employer and employee is primarily determined by the actions and attitudes of the employer. For instance, the employer generally sets the tone for whether the climate in the work environment will be casual, professional, regimented, creative, etc. The atmosphere that the employer desires to create will, therefore, determine whether the employer/employee relationships are healthy and productive. Whichever direction the employer chooses to take things, however, the importance of the employer-employee relationship cannot be overstated, as that relationship largely defines the organization and has far-reaching effects on company culture, employee satisfaction, and turnover rates. According to Nesco Resource, "When employees have a strong, healthy relationship with their employers, the entire company benefits, Studies show that employees who have mutually respectful relationships with their employers are more likely to be happy, loyal, and productive in the long-run."

Review of Literature:

Beardwell and Clayton (2008) in this sense, a literature review is a scholarly paper that presents the current knowledge including substantive findings as well as theoretical and methodological contributions to a particular topic. Literature reviews are secondary sources and do not report new or original experimental work. Most often associated with academic oriented literature, such reviews are found in academic journals and are not to be confused with book reviews, which may also appear in the same publication.

Moher et al (2009) Consideration of prior, relevant literature is essential for all research disciplines and all research projects. When reading an article, independent of discipline, the author begins by describing

previous research to map and assess the research area to motivate the aim of the study and justify the research question and hypotheses. This is generally referred to as the “literature review,” “theoretical framework,” or “research background.” However, for a literature review to become a proper research methodology, as with any other research, follow proper steps need to be followed and action taken to ensure the review is accurate, precise, and trustworthy. As with all research, the value of an academic review depends on what was done, what was found, and the clarity of reporting.

Torraco (2010) Depending on the purpose of the review, the researcher can use a number of strategies, standards, and guidelines developed especially for conducting a literature review. Then, when should a literature review be used as a research method. For a number of research questions, a literature review may be the best methodological tool to provide answers. For example, reviews are useful when the researcher wants to evaluate theory or evidence in a certain area or to examine the validity or accuracy of a certain theory or competing theories.

Henderson (2011) This approach can be narrow, such as investigating the effect of or relationship between two specific variables, or it can be broader, such as exploring the collective evidence in a certain research area. In addition, literature reviews are useful when the aim is to provide an overview of a certain issue or research problem. Typically, this type of literature review is conducted to evaluate the state of knowledge on a particular topic. It can be used, for example, to create research agendas, identify gaps in research, or simply discuss a particular matter. Literature reviews can also be useful if the aim is to engage in theory development

Marchington (2012) In these cases, a literature review provides the basis for building a new conceptual model or theory, and it can be valuable when aiming to map the development of a particular. Research field over time. However, it is important to note that depending on the goal of the literature review, the method that should be used will vary.

Wilkinson (2013) Systematic reviews have foremost been developed within medical science as a way to synthesize research findings in a systematic, transparent, and reproducible way and have been referred to as the gold standard among reviews Despite all the advantages of this method, its use has not been overly prevalent in business research, but it is increasing A systematic review can be explained as a research method and process for identifying and critically appraising relevant research, as well as for collecting and analyzing data from said research.

Limerick (2014) The aim of a systematic review is to identify all empirical evidence that fits the pre-specified inclusion criteria to answer a particular research question or hypothesis. By using explicit and systematic methods when reviewing articles and all available evidence, bias can be minimized, thus providing reliable findings from which conclusions can be drawn and decisions.

Objective of the Study:

The main objective of the present research work is to study the existing Industrial Relation in the organization. In order to obtain the objective the following sub hypothesis were framed.

- To find out the opinion of employees regarding the present employer - employee relations.
- To find out the opinion of employees about grievance redressal procedure.
- To find out the opinion of employees about employees participation in management and dispute settlement machinery.
- To find the effectiveness of training program.
- To suggest ways to improve the existing relation.

Need of the Study:

- The various significant features of Industrial Relation
- To help in the economic progress of a country.
- To help management both in the formulation of informed Industrial Relations policies and in their translation into action.
- To boost the discipline and morale of the Employees.
- To establish a pipeline between Employee and management.
- To help establishing and maintaining the industrial democracy which is a prerequisite as the establishment of a socialist society.

Research Design:

This study involves the descriptive research design. It includes surveys and fact findings of different kinds, which is one of the most suitable ways to carry out projects. The main purpose of this research design is it has no control over the variables. It gives report only what has happened or what is happening. The study was conducted for a period of 3 months. The type of research conducted was descriptive, because the employee’s opinions are qualitative in nature. It can only be analyzed and described. Descriptive research design In this research study, the researcher has used descriptive research design. Descriptive study, Who, What, When, Where, How are the questions for researcher to find their answers during the study. A descriptive study may be simple or 5 complex. This research study topic is according to the descriptive study. I have needed to find that all answers of these questions which come in descriptive study.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology is a way the systematically solve the research problem. Research methodology may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In this study the descriptive research design was adopted, since it includes surveys and fact- findings enquire of different kinds, which is one of the most suitable ways t carry out projects.

Limitations of the Study:

- While for certain dimensions, one need to use separate scales, no attempt, however, has been made in the present study in this regard. Some of the dimensions to the job satisfaction are measured using the response obtained for only one question. This could heavily restrict the generalization of the result of the study.
- The study cannot be generalized to the whole organization because the researcher could personally contact only the dayshift employee. However care is taken for reliable data.
- Since the topic chosen was very vast and sensitive the research limited the scope of the study to certain area

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Table Showing Gender of Respondents

S.No	Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Male	30	25%
2	Female	90	75%
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 75% of the respondents are belongs to male and 25%of the respondents are belongs to female. Thus, the majority of respondents are male

Table 2: Table Showing Educational Qualification of the Respondents

S.No	Educational Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	SSLC	24	20%
2	HSS	46	38%
3	UG	22	18%
4	PG	14	12%
5	Other Specific	14	12%
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 20% of the respondents belong to the SSLC, 38% of the respondents belong to HSS,18% of the respondents belong to UG, and 12% of the respondents belong to PG and 12% of the respondents other specific educational Qualification. Thus, the majority of respondents belong to HSS educational qualification

Table 3: Table Showing Experience of the Respondents

S.No	Experience	No of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
1	Below 5 Years	35	29%
2	Between 6-10 Years	24	20%
3	Between 11-15 Years	36	30%
4	Above 16 Years	25	21%
	Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

The above table shows that, 29% of the respondents experience below 5 years, 20% of the respondents experience is between 6-10 years, 30% of the respondents experience between 11-15 years and 21% of the respondents experience are above 16 years. Thus, the majority of the respondents experiences are between 11-15 years.

Findings:

- The majority of 33% of the respondents belong to the age group of 36-40
- The majority of the respondents about 75% are male.
- The majority of the respondents about 38% belong to HSS educational qualification
- The majority about 33% of the respondents have experience between 11-15 years.
- The majority about 34% of the respondents come under the income level of Rs.5001- Rs.10000.
- The majority about 66% of the respondents said the job suits their educational qualification

Suggestions:

- Recreational activities can be taken care of by the management.
- The organization should improve the benefit and services provided to the employee interest would be stimulated
- The company can make the benefit and services attractive to personnel.
- The employer should plan out the welfare activities in an effective way to improve the organization image in the eyes of the subordinates.

Conclusion:

A strong employer-employee relationship creates a pleasant work environment for the employee. Subsequently, he works with increased confidence and morale. This leads to better performance and increased. Organization to embrace the culture of employee empowerment, it must appreciate certain values such as appreciation, respect, and value for its employees. Good employer-employee relations are sure to have a positive impact on the growth and revenue of a company. This leads to a positive, happier and healthier and healthier work environment. This is not only reflected on the employer and employee, but also on the end customer associated with the organization, through enhanced productivity and quality. Hence, employer-employee relationship is key to the prospects of any organization and forms the backbone of the organization's progress.

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